

EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON ANTIMONY LEACHING FROM PET

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PLASTICS

- 1920. the first plastic polymer was synthesized

Plastics

390.7 Mt of plastics produced in 2021 (Plastic Europe, 2022)

PET is polymer used for carbonated soft drinks, mineral water, edible oils, juices and sauces, flasks, and transparent blister packaging.

583 billion PET bottles were produced in 2021 (www.statista.com)

Bottled water: 94 MPs/L

Plastics in the environment

Environmental Health Effects

PLASTIC IS NEW POLLUTANT

390.7 Mt of plastics produced in 2021 (*Plastic Europe, 2022*)

Only 9% of plastics produced since 1950 has been recycled

WHAT IS HAPPENING WITH PLASTIC IN THE ENVIRONMENT?

MICROPLASTICS/NANOPLASTICS

MPs: Microplastics are plastic pieces smaller than 5 mm

NPs: Nanoplastics are plastic pieces smaller than 1 μm

SECONDARY SOURCE: PRODUCTS OF PLASTICS DEGRADATION

- Sunlight exposure
- UV exposure
- Microorganisms
- Rain
- temperature
- saltwater

MICROPLASTICS (MPS)

PRIMARY SOURCE OF MPS

Cosmetic products

microbeads for scrubs and skin cleansers, gels, toothpastes..

Industrial products

as industrial raw materials, microfibers for the production of synthetic textiles, in the paint industry, etc.

Currently, microbeads are prohibited for use. The Netherlands were the first country to introduce a ban on microbeads in cosmetic products in 2014. Several countries, including Australia, Canada, Italy, Korea, New Zealand, Sweden, the UK and the US have followed suit.

Public interest is high

Science

Microplastic pollution discovered in snow near top of Mount Everest

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Many people climb Mt. Everest. But this tough trip requires lots of supplies and gear that don't always make it back down. Photo: John Harper/ Getty Images

By Doyle Rice, USA Today
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Microplastic pollution is everywhere. It's in the ocean. It's in our food. And now it's on Mount Everest.

Airborne plastic pollution 'spiralling around the globe', study finds

Rising levels of microplastic pollution raise questions about the impact on human health, experts say

▲ Microplastic pollution has been found on top of mountains such as the Forni glacier in Santa Caterina Valpurga, Italy. Photograph: Vittorio Zunino Celotto/Getty Images

Microplastic pollution is now "spiralling around the globe", according to a study of airborne plastic particles.

Plastic particles pass from mothers into foetuses, rat study shows

Nanoparticles found in foetal brains and hearts, but impact on human health is as yet unknown

▲ Microplastic pollution has reached every part of the planet, from the summit of Mount Everest to the deepest oceans. Photograph: iStock/Track Photo

Tiny plastic particles in the lungs of pregnant rats pass rapidly into the hearts, brains and other organs of their foetuses, research shows. It is the first study in a live mammal to show that the placenta does not block such particles.

Microplastics revealed in the placentas of unborn babies

This article is more than 3 months old

Health impact is unknown but scientists say particles may cause long-term damage to foetuses

▲ The oceans are teeming with microplastic pollution. Photograph: Shutterstock.com/istockphoto

Microplastic particles have been revealed in the placentas of unborn babies for the first time, which the researchers said was "a matter of great concern".

Recent research has revealed the presence of MPs in human blood, placenta....

MPS/NPS ARE NEW POLLUTANTS

- **Heavy metals**

- **Synergistic effects**

51 trillion particles float in the oceans

Synergistic effects (Trojan horse)

Microplastics can serve as vectors for different kind of contaminants: toxic metals, pesticides, antibiotics..

Plastic effects on human health

- ✓ Direct toxicity of MPs/NPs
- ✓ Ingestion: MPs can be ingested by food (sea food contain high content), by drinks (bottle water), salt, beer...

Salt: 700 MPs/Kg

Sea foods: 0.7- 7.8 MPs/g

Bottled water: 94 MPs/L

- ✓ Migration of MPs/NPs from food packaging
- ✓ **Some plastic additives can leach from plastic materials**

ANTIMONY IN DRINKING WATER

Sb used as a catalyst in PET production

Compare Sb content in water contained in PET bottles with water in bottles made of glass in Serbia

SB LEACHING FROM WATER BOTTLE MATERIALS

Our study has confirmed some “known” facts:

- 1) the presence of antimony in PET
200 - 400 mg/kg
- 2) Sb n.d in glass water Sb in PET from 1 to 5 µg/L
- 3) temperature increases antimony leaching (up to 10 µg/L)
- 4) Here is surprising difference of admitted levels between drinking and bottled water

European Union, 1998. EU directive 98/83/EC of 3rd November 1998 on the *quality of water intended for human consumption*. Official Journal of the European, Communities, 05/12/1998, L330/32-54.

5 µg/L Sb

European Union, 2011. Commission Regulation (EU) No. 10/2011 on *Plastic Materials and Articles Intended to Come into Contact With Food*.

40 µg/L

Germany is the only country that has an established limit for Sb in PET packaging, with a maximum limit of 350 mg/kg PET

PET/SB IN SOIL

32% of all plastic produced ends up in the soil therefore, soil is the primary sink for MPs.

MPs alter soil's physical structure

- ✓ reduce its ability to hold water
- ✓ alter the composition of soil microbial communities

MPs may generate different changes in soil properties such

- ✓ as pH and OM
- ✓ leading to different metal mobility

Consequently MPs have an impact on plants

PLANT AS AN INDICATOR

- ✓ increase bio-available Sb content in soil
- ✓ Other toxic element become more bioavailable for plant
- ✓ Higher accumulation of Sb in plant from soil enriched in PET

Distribution of microplastics in (sub)urban soils of Serbia and Cd, As, and Pb uptake by *Capsella bursa-pastoris* (L.) Medik

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TAKE HOME MESSAGES

- Combined pollution of MPs with toxic metals might intensify the risks to human health
- link between Sb concentration in water bottled in PET and the antimony in the polymer.
- Constant consumption of water with a high level of Sb can increase the level of cholesterol and also decrease blood sugar
- design of next generation of plastics

TAKE HOME MESSAGES

- Recycling, poor management of plastic waste have dramatically increased the amount of plastics in the environment
- Remediation techniques

Microplastic sources, reduction and remediation: current state and future trends

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THANK YOU

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